

A retrospective study on arsenic pollution in BDP areas – reasons and remedies[†]

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Abstract : The biogeochemical processes causing As-distribution in ground water of Bengal Delta Plain (BDP) areas are not well understood but As-mobilization in ground water are well known. Increased As-mobilization in ground water is due to increased manmade activities like mining, greater use of ammonium and particularly phosphates (as fertilizers, detergents, animal and plant wastes) and excess withdrawal of water causing depletion of water table. PO_4^{3-} and also NH_4^+ ions with minerals may cause displacement of As^{V} or As^{III} from arsenic bearing minerals. However, processes leading to the increase in As-mobilization in ground water (even in surface waters of ponds etc.) are expected to increase with increase in P and N-budget in soils and water and with heavy withdrawal of ground water to meet the demands of increased industrialization and population. Intake of As-polluted water is the destiny for rural people where underground arsenic pollution is known unless proper remedial measure like use of filters for As-removal from the polluted waters is undertaken.

Most of the filters contain granular ferric hydroxides/activated alumina or aluminium silicate with or without metal oxides/ion-exchange resins. The working principles are the selective adsorption of $\text{AsO}_3^{3-}/\text{AsO}_4^{3-}$, oxidation of AsO_3^{3-} to AsO_4^{3-} by iron hydroxides/oxides. The filtering capacity is dependent on pH but the capacity is affected by the presence of other ingredients like PO_4^{3-} , F^- , Cl^- ions etc. However, As-content in wells and As-removing ability of the filters are not uniform. Some aspects of As-removing capability together with the effects of interfering ions are discussed. The high Fe content at $\text{pH} > 7$ causes precipitation of Fe as colloidal ferric hydroxide having better As-adsorption capability. This helps greater removal of As but is associated with clogging of filter beds having the opposite effect affecting the discharge of water. Frequent cleaning helps the restoration As-removal capability to a greater extent but shortens the life span and reduction of As-removal capability leading to ultimate breakdown of the filters at the vulnerable points. Suitable measures must be taken to reduce the gradual clogging and reduction of As-removal capability in designing the filters. Attempts should be made to find alternative methods for low cost As-removal process from ground water.

Keywords : Arsenic pollution, ARUBA, BDP areas filters, low cost technologies, reasons, remedies.

Introduction

Arsenic accumulation in ground water is a burning problem in BDP areas or Ganga Padma delta basin of West Bengal and Bangladesh and in other countries like China, Burma, Nepal, Thailand etc. As-mobilization in water causes a wide range of diseases. Naturally, the causes of As-mobilization in underground water and the remedial measures for its amelioration are the subject matter of research, discussion and debate. Attempts are made to understand the causes of excess As-release or mobilization in water to undertake satisfactory remedial

measures for the removal of excess As-from potable water. Various theories have been proposed for As-release in ground water but the true reason appears to be elusive as yet.

Some of the reasons advanced for As-release in ground water are :

(1) Oxidation of arsenic rich pyrites in aquifer sediments¹⁻⁴ according to the eq. (1).

[†]In honour of Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar.

(2) Reduction of arsenic rich iron hydroxides in anoxic ground water⁵⁻¹⁰.

(3) As-mobilization in sediments using anaerobic metal reducing bacteria¹¹⁻¹⁴

It is apparent that the reasons of As-mobilization or accumulation are geochemical and microbial i.e. biogeochemical in nature and are dependent on the geographical, climatic and soil condition of the aquifers associated with other factors. However, the biogeochemical changes are natural processes and have been continuing for a long period. It can be assumed that there was As-release even in earlier periods (prior to 1980) in BDP or Ganga-Padma basin areas but the concentration of As was low as manifested outwardly from the absence of different indications of As-poisoning. This is tantamount to suggesting that the natural biogeochemical processes were slow and release of As was also meagre to cause contamination or damage.

Pollution or excessive As-mobilization in water can arise if one or more stages of biogeochemical processes are disturbed due to manmade activities. Some of these are :

Erosion, transportation and weathering of increased quantity of minerals obtained from the upper catchment areas due to extensive mining from the Himalayas, Chotonagpur plateau, Rajmahal hills and Shillong plateau and carried by the flowing meandering rivers cause deposition of As containing pyrites in the affected areas of BDP. The factors leading to subsequent release of As are :

(a) The alluvial soils of Ganga-Padma are highly impervious leading to low permeability of soils¹⁵ hindering the proper recharging of the aquifers during the rainy seasons. Moreover, greater and greater use of shallow pumps for intensive Boro cultivation and use of pumps for domestic purposes (to meet the needs of the ever increasing population) cause enormous depletion of the underground water table of aquifers. These result in the increase of As concentration in ground water.

(b) Water logging of the low lying BDP areas for a considerable period (2-3 months) during rainy season cause anoxic conditions to persist leading to reduction of As^V to As^{III} in soils and leached in water.

(4) Enormous increase of phosphorus (as phosphates mainly) from

a. Decay of human, animal and plant wastes.

b. Intensive use of detergents containing polyphosphates (and ultimately converted to phosphate), insecticides and phosphate fertilizers containing traces of As.

c. Extensive use of fireworks and low explosives containing appreciable quantity of As salts¹⁶

d. Increase of N-budget from ((NH₄)₂SO₄, NH₄NO₃ (fertilizers and explosives)) and from human, animal and plant wastes.

All these factors particularly excess use of fertilizers, detergents and heavy withdrawal of ground water are responsible for the changes in the natural biogeochemical processes leading to accumulation and release of As in ground water.

(5) Competitive exchange model between PO₄³⁻ and AsO₄³⁻ (with similar adsorption capabilities on the available sites)¹⁷ was thus suggested for explaining high levels of As release and mobilization in ground water.

The model is, however, rejected and the reasons cited are (Reports from different agencies¹⁸⁻²⁰).

(i) Increase in P-content in ground water with depth is not expected if phosphate (from fertilizers) comes from soil leaching.

(ii) Contrary to expectation, high phosphate concentration is not associated with low bicarbonate concentration and there is no negative correlation between P and As.

The reasons advanced and correlations as pointed out are not considered to be sound as a large number of complicated and relatively known interactions between soil and ground water are involved. Phosphate mobilizations have been continuing from early periods due to weathering of rocks, decaying of animal and plant products. It is known that P-budget in river water increased enormously in recent years²¹⁻²⁴. The actual increases of P (mainly as phosphates) coming from domestic, municipal, industrial and agricultural wastes are not estimated. Enormous withdrawal of water from the saturated zone of water table creates a zone of depression and results in the infiltration of pollutants and hazardous chemicals from agricultural outlets, septic tanks, municipal wastes, dumps etc. via fractures, faults etc. in the earth's crust^{25,26}. Moreover, recharging of the aquifers during the rainy season causes enormous intrusion of soluble phosphates, ammonium salts, nitrates and other ingredients along with the sediments and move down the aquifers²⁵. Phosphates are more soluble than arsenates and arsenites. Thus, greater concentration of P with depth is natural. Exposure of soluble

Fe^{II} and Mn^{II} in ground water to air or O₂ results in the deposits of insoluble Fe³⁺ and Mn²⁺ oxides produced by bacterial catalyzed processes. The impermeable deposits cause disturbance to water flow into the well from the water bearing aquifers. Transport of pollutants from the underground waste sites and infiltration from the surface due to rain is dependent on the ground water flow. The water table is usually affected at a point remote from the point of infiltration due to heavy and localized rainfall. The filtration of water through fractures, faults in the earth's crust *etc.* is always associated with contaminants and pollutants^{25,26}.

It is known that phosphates are immobilized in soils as Al³⁺, Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺, Ca²⁺ phosphates. The phosphates are also immobilized as organic phosphates (like inositol phosphate)^{23,24}. Systematic variations or uniform homogeneous soil or water profiles are not observed in soils, sediments and ground water due to the sequence of changes arising from soil and water transport, weathering, leaching, mobilization and accumulation of clays, chemicals and humus materials at different depths. The exact mechanism of P and As mobilization in the soils, sediments and ground water is not known. As mobilization must be the result of complex biogeochemical processes depending on pH, redox conditions, sorption processes and particularly microbial changes resulting in reductive dissolution of the oxides of metals such as Mn, Fe, Co and Ni from higher oxidation states to divalent ions and subsequent interactions with phosphates²³⁻²⁷.

Phosphorus (from organic and inorganic origins) is adsorbed by the alluvial BDP sediments and soils consisting of silicate clays such as kaolinite, montmorillonite and illite^{28,29}. The concentrations of phosphate in sediments, soils and water depend on the adsorption and exchange of P between sediment with water. Phosphate adsorption capacities of clays are dependent on alumina to silica molecular ratios and free metal (particularly Fe and Cu) content. Phosphate adsorption capacities also differ with the nature of the clay content. The adsorption capacities of the clays for phosphorus are : kaolinite (0.091 mg P g⁻¹), montmorillonite (0.746 mg P g⁻¹) and illite (2.51 mg P g⁻¹). The facts suggest that concentration of phosphate with depth depends with nature of the soils and other interactions and cannot be correlated with AsO₄³⁻ concentration²⁴⁻²⁹. In aquifers, there are continuous interchanges of ions between water and soils and the concentration of ions are always variable. Naturally As concentration in the aquifers cannot be uniformly distributed

as there is continuous contamination leading to As release and withdrawal of water. These are very much dependent on the nature of the soils and soil topography and these determine the movement of water containing As, P *etc.* in the aquifers.

The microbial activities of anaerobes in presence of large quantity of organic matters and nutrients like N, P under favorable pH produce bicarbonate in sufficient amounts. Thus a positive correlation between As, P and bicarbonates can not be made and the reasons cited for the rejection of the theory are not sound and acceptable. Rather the theory⁴ proposed for the increased As-release in ground water due to manmade activities appears tenable. It is to be noted that the average P and As in earth's crust are 1 g/kg (as salts or acid) and 0.0018 g/kg respectively³⁰. Naturally, enormous amounts P present as soluble phosphates and ammonium salt may cause preferential adsorption, exchange and even displacement of As salts.

However, whatever may be mechanisms¹⁻⁴ of As-enrichment in ground water, the greater release of As from biogeochemical or manmade activities can not be cured. Rather in view of rapid industrialization and population increases with accompanying demands for food and water, the manmade activities causing pollution and greater As-release will go unabated *i.e.* habitants have to consume contaminated water unless proper remedial measures are taken and when surface water from rivers and ponds are not available. In general, surface water/river waters are soft to marginally hard. Sedimentation with coagulation, filtration and disinfection processes is followed to supply potable water for public uses. The quality of ground water is usually better than surface water as it is relatively free from suspended impurities and bacteria due to strainer action of soils²⁵. Dissolved salts and minerals are present which are relatively free from health hazards.

To find out the effective way of As-reduction the prime importance though often neglected should be given to understand the water quality of ground water. Water quality is variable with time place, and depth. (depending on geographic/geologic and climatic conditions) and from aquifer to aquifer. In spite of limitations, average ground water qualities of the arsenic affected (BDP) areas in terms of physico-chemical parameters are given below :

Conductivity – moderate

Alkalinity – usually high

pH – above 7

$E_{h(\text{anoxic})} < 100 \text{ mV}$

$\text{Fe} > 0.5$, $\text{Mn} > 0.07$, $\text{HCO}_3^- > 192$, $\text{PO}_4^{3-} > 0.24$, $\text{Cl}^- > 0.22$, $\text{SO}_4^{2-} < 69$, $\text{NO}_3^- < 29$, $\text{DOC} < 3$ (in terms of mg L^{-1})³¹.

Correlation between ($\text{HCO}_3^-/\text{low } E_h/\text{PO}_4^{3-}/\text{negligible DO}$) with arsenic and between iron and arsenic appears to be positive in several cases though there is negative correlation between arsenic and sulphate. The presence of redox sensitive species (arsenic, iron and manganese) and other factors described before suggest that the ground water is anoxic in nature and AsO_4^{3-} is expected to be converted mostly to AsO_3^{3-} under anoxic conditions so that there is preponderance of AsO_3^{3-} over AsO_4^{3-} in ground water.

It is apparent that the natural processes are unable to remove As-from ground water and artificial processes are needed to remove As. It has been observed that water from deep tube wells invariably contains considerable amount of iron be it in As-affected or non As-affected areas. As is present as AsO_4^{3-} and AsO_3^{3-} to a variable extent. Thus, As-removal devices should remove As and Fe. There are a number of available As-removal technologies based on physico-chemical principles like co-precipitation, alum coagulation, sorption methods, use of activated alumina, use of ion-exchange resin and membrane techniques etc.³². Processes based on *in situ* purification of arsenic contaminated ground water using iron filings permeable wall or by making modified porous media by deposition of colloidal iron oxide on sand grains at intermediate pH and ionic strength have been reported^{32,33}.

It was believed by the Public Health Engineers that in Gangetic West Bengal, shallow tube well waters of medium depths (40–50 m) may be contaminated with As but their assumption of absence of As contamination at higher depths proved false. The tube wells with high As contamination were sealed. Only slightly or marginally affected tube wells were allowed to undergo filter media treatment for As-removal. The working of the removal devices like filters are based on physico-chemical principles like adsorption, co-precipitation and ion-exchange with or without suitable oxidizing agent to convert As^{III} to As^{V} .

In general, most of the filters contain granular ferric hydroxides/activated alumina or aluminium silicate with or without metal oxides/ion-exchange resins. As-reduction capacities of the filters are specified by the manufac-

tures. The working of three different filters in terms of As and Fe removal are presented in Tables 1–3. The efficiency of the filters in terms of As elimination is related to the nature of ground water. (Chemical quantity of ground water samples collected from Chakdah block is presented in Table 4 to have an idea regarding the quality of ground water in this region). In all cases, concentrations of As and Fe in water were determined before and after the withdrawal of water. In general, As content of the wells increases with depth of the tube well. However, neither As-content in wells nor the As-removal ability of the filters is uniform (Tables 1–3). The removal of As is essentially an adsorption process together with the oxidation of AsO_3^{3-} to AsO_4^{3-} in some cases. It is known that the environmental processes are not uniform and variations in the concentrations of ions including AsO_3^{3-} , AsO_4^{3-} , PO_4^{3-} etc. are expected. These may be due to :

- Flow of ground water conditions and interactions between soil and water with variable biological activities.
- Electrochemical reactions of exposed active mineral surface.
- Redox reactions of light bioactive elements³⁵.

A positive correlation between As-removal with concentrations of total iron content and total alkalinity was noticed in some cases. As-removal is affected by ions like PO_4^{3-} , F^- , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} though no systematic study has been made in this direction. A significant reduction in arsenate and arsenite adsorption in presence of phosphate (dependent of PO_4^{3-} concentration and pH) has been reported. The phosphate adsorption is greater than that of arsenate at higher pH but the trend is reversed for arsenite at lower pH³⁶. It is apparent that both AsO_4^{3-} and PO_4^{3-} compete for the same surface sites for adsorption where PO_4^{3-} is preferred but preferential AsO_3^{3-} adsorption has been observed at lower pH. The presence of sulfate does not influence arsenate adsorption but a considerable reduction is observed for arsenite adsorption below pH 7.0 and reduction increases with decreasing pH³⁶. However, a trend of decreasing arsenate and arsenite adsorption with increasing concentration of sulphate was reported by Wilker and Hering³⁷. The pH of ground water is generally alkaline resulting from the buffering actions due to phosphate and bicarbonate (with traces of ammonia in some cases). Under the experimental pH (7.2 to 7.5), iron is present predominantly as Fe^{3+} ion which is converted to colloidal ferric hydroxide or a bridged compound with greater surface area and greater adsorp-

tion capability. The increased iron concentration increases the removal of As. It is substantiated from the fact that As-removal was found to be less when the filter was washed to remove the precipitated iron and other ingredients from the surface of the filters. The granular ferric hydroxide filter appears to be better over activated alumina filters. However, in all cases quality of water and proper monitoring are important. These aspects have not been studied properly. It is desirable to study the effect of different ions on the working of the filters using spiked water samples with different ions singly and collectively.

It is desirable to determine the efficiency of the different filters based on the sound knowledge of the water quality obtained from different wells. Attempts should be made to improve the quality of the filters or prepare better filters at low cost considering the water quality of the underground water samples. The yield of a common hand operated tube well is generally 10–20 L/min. The filter unit attached at the delivery end of the tube well is such that the tube well water yield is more or less compatible with the flow rate through the filter bed. The bed is long enough to provide sufficient contact time to eliminate the arsenic load during flow through the bed. The grain size of the filter materials controls the hydraulic conductivity and the diameter of the bed is such that the flow rate matches the tube well delivery to a great extent. Again, the grain surfaces are likely to lose activity by prolonged use. So some extra materials are added to exploit the bed efficiently for its design life. In field, the flow rates match initially as per technical specifications and the bed perform well in removing arsenic. But within a short time deposition on the pores starts clogging the pore paths causing hindrance to the flow. It may lead to some congenial as well as problematic situations. The co-precipitate contains ferric compounds that may help elimination of arsenic and iron load and the lessening of flow rate increases contact time so that better As-removal is ensured but these decrease the rate of water discharge of water considerably. However, there arises a discrepancy between the tube well yield and filter bed yield. Increased periodical cleaning of filter bed shortens the life span and reduction of As-removal capacity of the filters but if the amount of clogging is high, extra stress may come on the pipes and the strainer during pumping. In many cases, there are found broken at some weak vulnerable points. Thus, the design or service life of the costly installed filter beds or filter columns seldom matches with the real service life. In view of these difficulties encountered, many

of the filter bed Arsenic treatment plants in West Bengal have become defunct. Naturally to have a good performance of such an absorptive filter bed throughout its designed life period, factors like gradual clogging and reduction of yield should be considered in the design and suitable corrective measures are to be adopted. It is seen that the arsenic removal processes based on filter treatment are costly, less efficient and are dependent on Government subsidy in developing countries like India, Bangladesh, Nepal etc. Therefore it is imperative that alternative efficient low cost – effective water treatment protocol has to be devised for As-removal from groundwater. There are definite simple methods for water treatment based on age old knowledge. Century old Faridpur (Bangladesh) water purification unit is a classic example where the ultraviolet radiation in sunlight and dissolved oxygen in water are used to oxidize toxic As^{III} to less toxic As^V to be precipitated as iron-arsenate and removed. Reduction of arsenic concentration from 220 ppm/l to 42 ppm/l is claimed to have been achieved³².

Another recent cost-effective technology is the use of readily available bottom ash from coal fired power plant. ARUBA (Arsenic Removal Using Bottom Ash) has proven effective in reducing high concentrations of arsenic ranging from 200 to 900 ppb to below 50 ppb. The time required for arsenic removal is moderate³⁸.

Thus, the use of low cost technology based on common knowledge and age old practice should be adopted. Groundwater should be taken in an open tank (size depending on requirements) containing laterite soils or iron hydroxide or soil with iron filings or simply soil at pH 7.0 to 8.0. The mixture should be kept exposed to sunlight and air for several hours. Further purification can be effected by passing decanted water successively through pebbles, charcoal and sand in two porous earthenware pots having outlets. Disinfection may be made if required. However, the Public Health Engineers of West Bengal prefer to opt for classical methods of treating surface water by passing through sand filtrates and alum dosing and chlorine dosing to precipitate the suspended matters from surface water. The process is safe, less costly and befit community demand.

N.B : Recently, a team of scientists from Pohang University of Science and Technology (South Korea) used RGO (a composite material made from reduced graphene oxide and magnetite) to remove arsenic effectively from drinking water. (Graphene is two dimensional allotroph of carbon discovered in 2004, having a thickness of an atom). (ACS Nano 16th June doi : 10.10.21/

nn1008897). However, the method has not been explored commercially nothing is known about the economic viability of the method.

Result

Improvement of water quality after passing through the granular filter bed

Table 1. Location of tube well – Hindupara, Kaliganj Block, Nadia
Depth of tube well – 29 meters
Filter medium – granular ferric hydroxide

Date	pH		As (mg/l)		Fe (mg/l)	
	Raw water	Raw water	Treated water	Raw water	Treated water	Treated water
17.01.03	7.2	0.230	0.052	2.130	0.340	
14.02.03	7.1	0.167	<0.010	2.070	0.210	
26.05.03	7.3	0.210	BDL	0.840	BDL	
24.07.03	7.9	0.121	BDL	1.150	BDL	
03.11.03	7.4	0.164	BDL	0.610	<0.200	
16.12.03	-	0.248	0.153	1.940	0.290	
28.04.04	7.8	0.239	BDL	2.810	<0.200	
19.07.04	7.4	0.328	0.043	3.350	0.310	
17.11.04	7.7	0.227	0.079	1.770	0.460	
13.01.05	7.5	0.167	0.059	2.910	0.660	
04.02.05	7.5	0.171	0.064	2.460	0.930	
12.04.05	7.7	0.304	0.165	6.940	1.290	
16.05.05	7.5	0.168	0.087	3.710	0.670	

*BDL = Below detection limit.

Table 2. Location of tube well – Near Kaminibala Primary School, Ranaghat-II, Nadia
Depth of tube well – 36.7 meters
Filter medium – Activated alumina

Date	pH		As (mg/l)		Fe (mg/l)	
	Raw water	Raw water	Treated water	Raw water	Treated water	Treated water
17.11.03	7.5	0.068	0.032	1.070	<0.200	
08.03.04	7.8	0.069	<0.010	1.650	<0.200	
28.04.04	7.7	0.063	0.025	1.090	0.230	
29.06.04	7.6	0.093	0.015	2.230	0.260	
13.07.04	7.8	0.059	0.032	3.360	0.410	
14.09.04	7.8	0.072	0.024	3.450	0.860	
08.10.04	7.8	0.047	0.018	1.580	<0.200	
16.11.04	7.8	0.039	BDL	1.070	<0.200	
20.12.04	7.4	0.123	<0.010	2.530	<0.200	
05.01.05	7.8	0.097	0.029	2.870	0.350	
29.03.05	7.6	0.095	0.071	1.570	0.460	
04.06.05	7.5	0.121	0.034	1.670	<0.200	

Source : Monitoring reports of treatment plants; P.H.E. Dte., West Bengal (2003, 2004, 2005).

Table 3. Location of tube well – Anjararh, Ranaghat-I, Nadia
Depth of tube well – 41 meters
Filter medium – activated alumina

Date	pH	As (mg/l)		Fe (mg/l)	
		Raw water	Treated water	Raw water	Treated water
27.11.03	7.3	0.067	0.031	0.790	<0.200
29.01.04	7.4	0.108	0.037	0.970	<0.200
18.06.04	7.6	0.129	0.047	1.570	0.710
23.07.04	7.5	0.083	0.014	0.940	<0.200
30.09.04	-	0.091	0.042	2.430	0.560
19.11.04	7.4	0.122	0.068	2.830	0.310
23.12.04	7.6	0.153	0.104	1.890	1.150
14.01.05	7.8	0.121	0.073	3.170	0.450
31.03.05	7.6	0.093	0.064	2.090	0.380
18.04.05	7.7	0.075	0.054	1.810	0.450
16.05.05	7.4	0.105	0.054	1.740	0.460
13.06.05	7.6	0.119	0.074	2.310	0.930

Table 4. Chemical quality of some ground water samples collected from Chakdah Block, Nadia

Sample no.	1	2	24	28
Address	Sukantapalli	Bunlia	Pritinagar	Lalpur
E _h (mV)	-127	-94	-92	-127
Depth (meter)	25	21	69	130
Temperature (°C)	28	27.6	27	28.8
pH	6.69	6.65	6.97	6.57
Cond. (µs/cm)	763	651	483	714
DO (mg/l)	0	0.12	0	0
Ca (mg/l)	94.9	91.8	78.1	97.1
Na (mg/l)	29.3	16.8	10.0	25.2
Mg (mg/l)	27.6	25.5	14.1	26.0
K (mg/l)	3.1	1.9	2.4	2.6
Fe (mg/l)	6.6	4.6	2.9	2.2
Al (mg/l)	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.03
Mn (mg/l)	0.33	0.70	0.53	0.07
F (mg/l)	0	3.94	3.10	0
Cl (mg/l)	7.1	5.9	3.1	5.2
NO ₃ (mg/l)	29.10	1.06	0	1.94
PO ₄ (mg/l)	0.95	0.24	0.48	0.52
SO ₄ (mg/l)	21.50	2.40	0	2.14
HCO ₃ (mg/l)	599	210	437	327
DOC (mg/l)	2.59	1.39	0.67	0.28
As ^{III} (mg/l)	0.163	0.028	0.028	0.034
As (mg/l)	0.243	0.041	0.059	0.055

Source : Joydev Jana (2002); Genesis of Arseniferous Ground Water in the Bengal Delta Plains in West Bengal, Eastern India. PhD thesis submitted to University of Kalyani.

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